

Amitriptyline dependence and withdrawal delirium in an adult: A case report

Contributors

1. Dr. Pirzada Zahid Zia , Post Graduate, Department of Psychiatry, VMKVMCH, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (DU), Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.
2. Dr. Ayush Lall, MD Psychiatry, Psychiatrist, State mental health hospital Sendri, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India
3. Dr. Pradeep. C, MD Psychiatry, Associate professor, Department of Psychiatry, VMKVMCH, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (DU), Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.
4. Dr. Lakshmi Dorai B , MD Psychiatry, Professor and HOD, Department of Psychiatry, VMKVMCH, Vinayaka Mission's Research Foundation (DU), Salem, Tamil Nadu, India.

Corresponding Author:

Name: Dr. Pirzada Zahid Zia

Post Graduate, Department of Psychiatry, Vinayaka Mission's

Kirupananda Variyar Medical College & Hospital, Salem, VMRF (DU),

Address: Room 3, F – Block, Pg boys Hostel, VMKVMCH, Chinnasiragapadi, Salem,

Tamil Nadu, India – 636308.

Key-words: Amitriptyline, Drug Dependence, Psychopharmacology

Introduction:

Amitriptyline acts by blocking the re-uptake pumps for norepinephrine and serotonin with receptor affinity towards histamine type 1, α 1-adrenergic and muscarinic cholinergic receptors.¹ Its usage other than antidepressants has expanded for anxiety, insomnia and chronic pain as an off-label drug.² Highest prevalence of off-label indications among other drugs is of tricyclic antidepressants, majorly amitriptyline.³ In the Indian population off-label use is seen mostly for somatic symptoms like headache.⁴

Starting with first case report for tricyclic antidepressant misuse in 1970, amitriptyline is seen to produce euphoria, pleasant or high feelings.⁵ Amitriptyline with its large off-label usage, carries potential of dependence which still is less explored and thus lacks awareness among healthcare providers.⁵

Case history:

A middle age man, who works as a weaver, had head trauma seven months back under alcohol intoxication. Thereafter he had reduced sleep, headache, and body pain for which he was prescribed oral amitriptyline 25mg/day. After four days of consumption, with improvement in symptoms, he discontinued the drug for one month. Patient resumed its consumption by himself considering previous euphoric experiences and physical benefits. Over six months, tolerance developed and its consumption increased from two tablets to ten tablets of 25mg amitriptyline. Patient ignored warnings by his wife and the pharmacist of its side effect. Patient always carried five-six tablets of amitriptyline in his pocket, as he feared not getting medicines in his desired time. Patient never tried to lower the consumption.

Patient also had small eruptions on his forehead and thus had orthopedics' consultation leading to restricted consumption of amitriptyline up to 12.5mg/day, followed by hand tremors and giddiness throughout the day, reduced interaction, appetite and sleep duration, and had slowness in his daily activities. After two days, patient got admitted to the hospital where he misidentified the hospital as his workplace, and was unable to recognize his wife. On RASS scale, scores fluctuated from +2 to -2 in a day, and on the CAM-ICU scale had inattention, disorganized thinking, and altered level of consciousness. Past history of alcohol consumption for 20 years, discontinued seven months back due to head trauma. Patient had no significant family history. Vitals stayed within normal limits and no neurological deficit was observed. In CT Brain, no abnormality involving brain parenchyma was detected and blood investigations including serum electrolytes and renal function test were within normal limits.

Oral form of risperidone 4mg and lorazepam 2mg showed improvement within three days of hospital stay. Multiple swelling over the forehead diagnosed as craniofacial osteoma received conservative treatment. Patient was discharged with medicines and continued for follow-up in which lorazepam was tapered. Patient had improvement in his bio-socio-occupational functions.

Discussion:

This case provides the unique knowledge of discernible dependence pattern involving craving, tolerance, and increased consumption for physical benefits, despite being informed of side effects and was followed by delirium when discontinued. Epidemiological data on its misuse is required, thereby creating awareness for regular screening of its dependence pattern as amitriptyline is used in the multidisciplinary field as off labeled drug.⁵

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